

Design of real time vehicles over load monitoring system based on IoT

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Abstract

Due to the development of road infrastructure and business trade, transportation of goods is increasing day-by-day. Each vehicle has its own configuration, size, power and capacity. However, heavy vehicles are often used to carry loads beyond their capacity. Therefore, overloading is one of the major problems which affect truckers as well as other motorists and pedestrians going near-by. In order to provide a convenient solution to this problem, a web-based tracking system is proposed. A heavy-duty vehicle which is overloaded and moving at high speed may cause the vehicle to lose balance while making turns along the roads. This problem may also cause the tire to burst, which in turn makes it difficult to control the vehicle. Weighing stations may be the answer to these conditions, but few are used for measuring the weight of some specific vehicles in India. A vehicle loading monitoring detection using a load sensor and GSM model with an automatic engine lock system is proposed in this study as a solution. The proposed system will detect vehicle overloading and automatically call the owner of the vehicle or the road safety officer in that event. Proteus software is used for designing and simulating the circuit while programming is done using the Arduino software. Microcontroller serves as the brain of the design and Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) module serves as the communication link. A Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) is used to display the status of the vehicle. In addition, a buzzer is to sound an alarm when vehicle overloading is detected. The system has facilities to lock a vehicle engine automatically. This model solves the problem of real-time load detection in heavy vehicles and proposes a monitoring system for transportation. We aim to completely change the dynamics of this industry in India itself. This product will be revolutionary and will definitely reduce the frequency of road accidents & don't forget it will also reduce the wear & tear of the roads of our country and increasing their life.

Keywords: Microcontroller, Load Sensor for detection, GSM for Communication.

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1. Introduction

Transportation is the backbone of today's complex infrastructural world. Heavy-duty vehicles are used for transporting heavy load goods from one place to another. But the major problem also is integrated in this. Due to heavy loads and long distances, they pose a major threat to themselves and other vehicles on the road, as well as pedestrians [1]. A genetic neural network compensation algorithm is proposed to compensate for the disturbance signals [2]. Friction torque and disturbances are the main factor that influences dynamic response performance of high accuracy of servo systems. To compensate for the friction torque and other disturbances, a compound control strategy based on acceleration control and disturbance compound compensation is proposed [3]. Nowadays there is no facility to check the heaviness of the vehicle in tollgate. This work is implemented on tollgate area to detect the load carried by the vehicle using weight sensor [4]. It is observed that due to the development of road infrastructure and business trade, transportation of goods is increasing day-by-day. Each vehicle has its own configuration, size, power and capacity. However, heavy vehicles are often used to carry loads beyond their capacity. They become the reason for accidents and damage to property, infrastructure and threat to the lives of people [5]. They not only damage other vehicles, but also the goods and products in these trucks which can cause the loss of a lot of money. With the rapid development of the market economy, the volume of road freight is growing rapidly. At the same time, the overloading of trucks has become more and more serious. It is necessary to accurately monitor loading capacity in real time. Although the truck weighing technology has achieved a breakthrough in theoretical field, it made high financing costs and low accuracy [6]. An integrated GPS-GSM system is proposed to track vehicles using Google Earth application. The remote module has a GPS mounted on the moving vehicle to identify its current position, and to be transferred by GSM with other parameters acquired by the automobile's data port as an SMS to a recipient station. The received GPS coordinates are filtered using a Kalman filter to enhance the accuracy of measured position [7-8]. Also, Overloaded vehicles can cause the tires to overheat and wear rapidly which increases the chance of premature, dangerous and expensive failure or blow-outs [9]. They propose a systematic framework of truck

overload intelligent monitoring system under the concept of internet of things (IOT) to solve the truck's ever-increasing serious overload problem in China. First the overviews of general concept of IOT and its Chinese version, Sensing China, are introduced to provide the background information. Next, the serious truck overload problem in China is explained in details including data summary of casualties and monetary cost caused by overload [10-11]. Overloading decreases the stability of the vehicle and makes it tough for the driver to control the vehicle in different road conditions. Overloading causes excessive wear and tear of automobile components like bearings, suspension systems, gearbox, engine, tire, brake shoes etc. Overloading also decreases the braking efficiency as the braking distance is increased [12-13].

While there are Weighing stations present at different places, but they are far away from the loading points and hence accidents can happen in that transit. Also, many drivers don't feel the need of weighing their trucks or don't weigh their trucks deliberately in the hope of high profits. But this act of theirs increases the risk of accidents [14].

We are making a vehicle loading monitoring detection using a load sensor and GSM model with an automatic engine lock system is proposed in this study as a solution. The proposed system will detect vehicle overloading and automatically call the owner of the vehicle or the road safety officer in that event. Proteus software is used for designing and simulating the circuit while programming is done using the Arduino software. Microcontroller ESP 8266 serves as the brain of the design and Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) module serves as the communication link. A Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) is used to display the status of the vehicle. In addition, a buzzer is to sound an alarm when vehicle overloading is detected. The system has facilities to lock a vehicle engine automatically. We are proposing a vehicle loading monitoring system using a load sensor with an automatic engine lock system and GSM model for call alert to monitor their weight when being loaded. This system will help vehicle owners and road safety personnel to detect a vehicle's status when overloading detection occurs through a call alert notification. Furthermore, an early warning of overloading will be issued to the vehicle's driver

or the person loading the vehicle to avoid exceeding the vehicle's gross weight.

In India, Overloaded vehicles accounted for 10% of total accidents, 12% of fatalities and 27% of injuries, as per the 2018 Ministry of Road, Transport and Highways report. According to statistics, more than 80% of truck-related crashes result from truck overloading [15]. Hence, it becomes important to solve such a problem and which is causing such a big damage to the infrastructure of this country.

The methodology is divided into two parts. The first part is on the mechanical schematics, followed by hardware description and the finally on the programming design. All parts were assembled together and experiments were then performed to determine the working.

A. Mechanical Design Structure - For the main structure of the device, to get the preferred work, we have microcontroller as the brain. The GSM Module has the ability to send signals to other locations. The power supply provides and supply and is regulated by Voltage regulator. The signals from Load sensor are send to microcontroller and then to the GSM module in case of overloading. The LCD displays the status and the buzzer sounds.

B. Software programming - The microcontroller is programmed with necessary data and information of the pre-determined threshold values of Load and its proportionate voltages. The following is done by Arduino software. The GSM module is also interconnected with the microcontroller.

2. Objective of the project

The main objective of this paper and project is to study and develop a technology or device for detect an overloading situation in a heavy vehicle and hence stop it from moving by shutting off its engine. The scope of the project in the transportation sector is vast, especially in the heavy-vehicle segment or sector. The main operation of the device is to detect overloading and stop the vehicle, sound the buzzer and send an SMS regarding the same to the owner of the vehicle. It is a continuously working device and reflects the status of vehicle load in real-time on the LCD. It has the capacity and range to detect

overloading in one place/vehicle and alert the owner and the respective authorities in another place.

3. Scope of the project

The main scope of project is to detect load in any vehicle and stop the engine in case of overloading. It can send SMS to the authorities and the owner about the same. It will give an early warning in overloading situation and will sound the buzzer and reflect the status on LCD in real-time. By it the frequency of road accidents and wear & tear of roads will increase and hence will save a lot of lives and will reduce the financial losses associated with the same.

4. Material and Methodology

4.1 Block Diagram

Figure 4.1 below shows the block diagram of the blue print of the proposed vehicle overloading monitoring system with an automatic engine lock and a call alert. It consists of a microcontroller, GSM module, power supply, keypad, LCD display, DC motor (car engine), load sensor, buzzer and an engine control block.

Figure 4.1: Block Diagram of Working Model

Source: Authors.

4.2 Materials

1. Microcontroller;
2. Load Sensor;
3. GSM Module;
4. Power Supply;
5. Voltage Regulator;
6. Buzzer;
7. Voltmeter.

4.1 Microcontroller

Microcontroller is the brain of the device which is programmed to receive an input from the load sensor. It is challenging to interface two communication GPS and GSM modules with one serial UART.

The Microcontroller has the following functions. It

- I. Serves as the brain of the design and Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) module serves as the communication link;
- II. Is programmed to receive an input from the load sensor;
- III. Provides way of processing and control unit for automotive modules;
- IV. Makes implementation of hardware projects more in-line with the needs of actual engineering.

4.2 Load Sensor

Load sensor is the component which detects the load and the main objective of the load sensor are high sensitivity, stability, more coverage area, accuracy, low cost, long life. The load sensor is nothing but weight sensor, calculate the load without any calibrated values.

For leaf spring suspension axle load can be calculated with 5 -7% error from the maximum axle load. And total vehicle load can be calculated with 5-10% error from vehicle's gross weight (or vehicle + trailer). For air spring suspension: 2-3% error of the maximum axle load and 3-5% error from vehicle's gross weight. Load sensor is an electronic device that converts tension and compression forces into a corresponding electrical signal. A load (weight) can be applied to a platform of the load cell and the load can be sensed and split the load to multiple load cells near in the platform (coverage cells). Load sensor is designed for load control and cargo weight control in vehicle tracking systems. Load sensor can be connected to the analog input of tracking device. With load sensor, a vehicle tracking system gets valuable information about the location and time of loading and unloading the vehicle. Load sensor passes the information on raising or lowering the load on axle to terminal.

Vehicle tracking system with the help of GPS determines the location and time.

Figure 4.2: Load Sensor.

Source: Authors.

4.3 GSM Module

A customized Global System for Mobile communication (GSM) module is designed for wireless radiation monitoring through Short Messaging Service (SMS). This module is able to receive serial data from radiation monitoring devices such as survey meter or area monitor and transmit the data as text SMS to a host server.

4.4 Power Supply

Power supply is a device that converts the output from an AC power line to a steady dc output or multiple outputs. The ac voltage is first rectified to provide a pulsating dc and then filtered to produce a smooth voltage. The power supply consists of a 12 V DC battery which supplies the entire circuit, and the engine starter. Purpose of a Power Supply is to convert AC to DC and provide DC voltage to the motherboard, adapters, and peripheral devices. It Provide cooling and facilitate air flow through the case.

4.5 Voltage Regulator

The voltage regulator is one kind of electrical component used to maintain a stable voltage across any electronic device. The fluctuations in the voltage can cause an undesirable cause in an electronic system. For that, maintaining a stable voltage is compulsory based on the system voltage requirement. The voltage is regulated from 12VDC to 5VDC and then sent to the

microcontroller, which is programmed to receive an input from the load sensor.

4.6 Buzzer

A buzzer is a small yet efficient component to add sound features to our project/system. It is very small and compact 2-pin structure hence can be easily used on breadboard, Perf Board and even on PCBs which makes this a widely used component in most electronic applications.

This buzzer can be used by simply powering it using a DC power supply ranging from 4V to 9V. A simple 9V battery can also be used, but it is recommended to use a regulated +5V or +6V DC supply. The buzzer is normally associated with a switching circuit to turn ON or turn OFF the buzzer at required time and require interval.

5. Methodology

The power supply is taken from the 12VDC battery that supplies the engine start relay. This relay provides a seal-in for current to flow through the normally closed (NC) contact of the engine lock relay (RL4) to the car engine. On ignition, supply voltage from the battery goes to terminal (1) of the voltage regulator (7805) while terminal 3 is connected to the AVCC terminal of ESP 8266 microcontroller and terminal 2 connected to ground. The 7805 reduces the input voltage of 12VDC to 5VDC to supply the microcontroller ESP 8266. At normal condition when overloading is not detected, the signals (voltage) from the load sensor to the ESP 8266 sensor input pin INT13 will be within the set point so the output signals from the microcontroller to the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) shows the normal condition of the vehicle. When overloading is detected, a signal (voltage) which is above the set point will be sent to the microcontroller from the overloading sensor. The output signal from pin INT18 of the microcontroller is sent to the engine lock switch relay (RL1) through the base resistor to the NPN transistor Q1 to switch it on to energize the relay coil. When the coil of the relay is energized, its normally opened contact closes and power at the normally opened contact of the RL1 is transferred to the buzzer to sound an alarm. At this point, the coil of the engine lock is energized and that opens the engine circuitry to prevent power from reaching the engine, as a result establishing the engine lock condition. When this happens, the

Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) indicates overloading detected. The microcontroller sends a signal to the GSM module SIM800L connected to the transmitter terminal INT16 and the receiver terminal INT17 to automatically call the owner of the vehicle (an authorized person). To bring the engine back to its normal operating mode, the authorized person must enter the recovery code using the keypad. When overloading is detected, before the recovery code is entered, the load in the vehicle must be reduced (or removed) so that the code will be able to activate the system. When the correct code is dialed, it sends a signal from INT19 terminal of the ESP 8266 at microcontroller to the base of the transistor Q2 through the 1kΩ resistor to switch it on. When the transistor Q2 is switched on, current flows through the collector of Q2 to the engine recovery relay coil to energize it. The normally closed (NC) contact of Q2 opens to prevent current from flowing through the engine lock relay which de-energizes the engine lock relay. This closes the vehicle engine circuitry to allow the engine to turn on when the ignition key is activated. The reset button is used to reset ESP 8266 microcontroller when an error occurs. Variable resistor (RV2) is used to increase and decrease the resolution (brightness) of the LCD screen. The DC motor and the buzzer are supplied with 12VDC from the battery anytime the ignition key is activated. A voltmeter is connected to measure the voltage signal of the load sensor anytime a load is placed in the vehicle.

Figure 5.1: Circuit diagram of Vehicle Loading Monitoring with an automatic engine lock system based on GSM.

Source: Authors.

6. Experiments results

Figure 6.1: Working Model.

Source: Authors.

Table 1: Experimental results of the overloading sensor.

NE	Sensor (IR)*	W. L. (g)	ODS
1	0	0	Not detected
2	10	99	Not detected
3	20	195	Not detected
4	30	351	Not detected
5	40	460	Detected
6	50	510	Detected

Note: NE: Number of Experiment; *Sensor (IR) Readings in Percentage (%); **Weight of Load (g); ODS: Overload Detection State. **Source:** Authors.

Figure 6.2: Graph of load sensor reading in percentage (%) against rising level of sensor.

Source: Authors.

The Table (1) below shows the experimental results of the overloading sensor. The load sensor reading is presented in percentage (%) against the rising level of the sensor.

The graphical representation of the experimental results shown in Table (1) is shown in Figures (5.1, 6.1, 6.2).

7. Discussion

Table 5.1 Show the result for a prototype vehicle overloading prevention system that uses a load sensor with an automatic engine lock and call alert system. In each of the tests, the load sensor was subjected to different weights until overloading was detected. At each percentage, the status of the vehicle was sent from the virtual terminals of the microcontroller ESP 8266 to the screen of the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) to indicate the condition of the vehicle until overloading was detected. In all, seven experiments were conducted at different ranges of the load sensor levels. The 0% gives a zero gram (0 g) of weight indicating the normal load sensor condition of 47 the vehicle when there is no load in the vehicle. The LCD indicates that overloading is not detected. The percentage up to 49% which gives its equivalent weight of 498g which shows the maximum weight of load the vehicle can carry for which overloading is not detected. The microcontroller compares the set point value to the signal from the sensor. The microcontroller is programmed such that if the difference in value exceeds the normal weight of the vehicle, it sends information about the excess weight to the engine lock relay to activate it as it is programmed to lock the engine of the vehicle. Any percentage with its corresponding weight above 50% and 460g will indicate the maximum level at which overloading is detected. The system will then call the owner of the vehicle automatically. Again, Figure 5.2 shows the minimum and maximum levels within which overloading can be detected.

7. Conclusions

The testing and validation of the logical (flow chart) model was successfully achieved by using a simulation software package (Proteus) and Arduino programming software. The experimental device after it was designed; it was simulated before used in construction of the artifact. Design

and construction of the vehicle loading monitoring system was successfully accomplished. The prototype worked exactly as a real-time system during demonstration. GSM SIM800L module was used as communication link for the system to call the vehicle owner automatically under overload condition. The vehicle load monitoring system is proposed with the aim of solving the problem of the inability of some vehicle drivers to access axle weighing stations to weigh the load their vehicles carry due to the limited number of weighing stations available in Ghana. To help stop vehicle overloading in Ghana, it is recommended, the proposed vehicle loading monitoring system is implemented. The engine lock system could prevent vehicle breakdown as well as accidents. This could potentially replace existing technology where drivers have to wait for hours at weighing stations before their vehicles' gross weight is captured using weighing sensors installed in roadway concrete. Implementing this technology in vehicles in Ghana or anywhere in the world will help to reduce overloading, which usually leads to road accidents and infrastructure deterioration.

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